

Assessment of Knowledge, Attitude and Practice of Antibiotic Usage Among Undergraduate, Intern, and Postgraduate Dental Students: A Questionnaire Based Study

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ABSTRACT

Background: The aim of the present study was to assess the knowledge, attitude and practices among UG, Intern & PG dental students towards the antibiotic usage, resistance and prescription. **Objective:** To educate and spread awareness about the use of antibiotic and its resistance among health care professional students. **Methods:** This was a cross sectional questionnaire based study conducted among the UG, Intern & PG dental students studying in a teaching hospital RDDC & research centre, Nagpur. After obtaining the consent from the participants, questionnaire was distributed to evaluate their knowledge, attitude and practice towards antibiotic usage, resistance and prescription. The responses were collected, compiled and data was analysed. **Result :** Overall 150 students participated in this study. A significant difference was observed in the knowledge and practice of the three groups. A pairwise comparison showed that practice was significantly better among PG students as compared to the UG students. **Conclusions:** This study shows the KAP of budding health-care professionals in a real ground situation in our academics and the role of awareness about antibiotic use in health care which can help in preventing the emergence of antibiotic resistance. It provides useful information to plan a suitable educational intervention for rationale antibiotic use and to minimize resistance.

KEYWORDS: Antibiotic usage, resistance, prescribing policy, Public health.

INTRODUCTION:

The overuse and misuse of antibiotics pose a significant threat to global public health, leading to the emergence of antibiotic resistance. Dental practitioners, including undergraduate, intern, and postgraduate dental students, play a crucial role in antibiotic stewardship due to their frequent prescription of antibiotics for oral infections. The aim of this to evaluate the current literature regarding the knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) of antibiotic usage among dental students at different stages of their education.

METHOD

This study was questionnaire based single cross-sectional study done amongst 150 dental students from RDDC & RESEARCH CENTRE, NAGPUR in which 60 undergraduates (3rd year-30 and 4th year-30), 60 interns and 30 postgraduates included. A modified questionnaire was made which consist of 2 parts; Part 1 of the questionnaire included demographic data of the participants like age, gender and Part 2 contained questionnaire to assess the participant's knowledge (5 questions), attitude (5 questions) and practice (5 questions) regarding the antibiotic use and its resistance. After taking informed consent from the participants, questionnaire was distributed. The response for knowledge based questions was assessed in terms of 'true' or 'false', and attitude and practice based questions are assessed in terms of 'yes' or 'no'. The performance was assessed by score (correct response = 1, incorrect response=0) and total scores obtained was calculated.

QUESTIONNAIRE

1. Antibiotic can cure infections caused by virus??	A)True b)False
2. The use of antibiotics will speed up the recovery of cold and cough??	A)True b)False
3. Super infection is an adverse effect of antibiotic use?	A)True b)False
4. Indiscriminate use of antibiotics leads to emergence of antibiotic resistance?	A)True b)False
5. Efficacy better, if the antibiotics are newer and costlier?	A)True b)False
6. Do you think there is abuse on antibiotics at present?	A)Yes b) No
7. Do you think antibiotic resistance	A)Yes b) No

affects you and your family's health?	
8. Do you think skipping one or two doses of antibiotic does not contribute to the development of antibiotic resistance?	A)Yes b) No
9. Do you think adverse effects can be reduced by using more than two antibiotics at a time?	A)Yes b) No
10. Abuse of antibiotics has become the main cause leading to bacterial resistance?	A)Yes b) No
11. Have you ever taken any antibiotic without physician consultation?	A)Yes b) No
12. Do you take the full course of antibiotics prescribed by the doctor?	A)Yes b) No
13. Do you stop taking antibiotics when you start feeling better?	A)Yes b) No
14. Do you save the leftover antibiotics for the future use?	A)Yes b) No
15. Do you give the leftover antibiotics to your friend / roommate if they get sick?	A)Yes b) No

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS :

Data was analyzed using SPSS v26 software. The level of significance was kept at 5%. Results were presented using descriptive statistics. Gender distribution was presented using frequency and percentage. Comparison of knowledge, attitude and practice among three study groups was done using Kruskal Wallis test followed by multiple comparisons using Boneferroni correction.

RESULT

Overall, 150 dental students from RDDC & RESEARCH CENTRE, NAGPUR in which 60 undergraduates (3rd year-30 and 4th year-30), 60 interns and 30 postgraduates took participation in the KAP study of antibiotic use, self-medication, and antibiotic resistance. Gender distribution is depicted in Table-1 where it is clearly shown that females are higher compared to males.

Based on KAP scores obtained an overall significant difference was seen in the knowledge of the three groups with PG students showing greater knowledge as compared to the other two groups as shown in Table-2. However, overall non-significant difference was seen in the attitude of the three groups as shown in Table-3. An overall significant difference was seen in the practice of the three groups with a greater no of PG students showing good practices as compared to the other two groups seen in Table-4.

Gender distribution among UG, Interns, and PG students

Group		Female	Male	Total
UG	N	43	17	60
	%	71.70%	28.30%	100.00%
Interns	N	32	28	60
	%	53.30%	46.70%	100.00%
PG	N	23	7	30
	%	76.70%	23.30%	100.00%
Total	N	98	52	150
	%	65.30%	34.70%	100.00%

Table-1

Distribution of knowledge scores among UG, Interns, and PG students

Group		Good	Fair	Poor	p-value
UG	n	23	32	5	0.021*
	%	38.30%	53.30%	8.30%	

Interns	n	19	36	5
	%	31.70%	60.00%	8.30%
PG	n	18	12	0
	%	60.00%	40.00%	0.00%
Total	n	60	80	10
	%	40.00%	53.30%	6.70%

Table-2

An overall significant difference was seen in the knowledge of the three groups with PG students showing greater knowledge as compared to the other two groups. A pairwise comparison showed that knowledge was significantly lesser among interns as compared to the PG students.

Distribution of attitude scores among UG, Interns, and PG students

Group		Good	Fair	Poor	p-value
UG	n	39	21	0	0.478
	%	65.00%	35.00%	0.00%	
Interns	n	45	15	0	
	%	75.00%	25.00%	0.00%	
PG	n	22	7	1	
	%	73.30%	23.30%	3.30%	
Total	n	106	43	1	
	%	70.70%	28.70%	0.70%	

Table-3

An overall non-significant difference was seen in the attitude of the three groups with a majority of the subjects from all the three groups showing good attitude.

Distribution of practice scores among UG, Interns, and PG students

Group		Good	Fair	Poor	p-value
UG	n	9	31	20	0.008*
	%	15.00%	51.70%	33.30%	
Interns	n	16	27	17	
	%	26.70%	45.00%	28.30%	
PG	n	15	10	5	
	%	50.00%	33.30%	16.70%	
Total	n	28	75	47	
	%	18.70%	50.00%	31.30%	

Table-4

An overall significant difference was seen in the practice of the three groups with a with a greater no of PG students showing good practices as compared to the other two groups. A pairwise comparison showed that practice was significantly better among PG students as compared to the UG students.

DISCUSSION

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) has emerged as a significant global health crisis, leading to increased morbidity and mortality associated with infections. Dentists are notable contributors to antibiotic prescriptions, making it vital to evaluate their knowledge and practices regarding appropriate antibiotic use. A questionnaire can effectively gather quantitative data from dental students, facilitating an understanding of their awareness and attitudes towards antibiotic usage. The present study is undertaken amongst Undergraduate (UG), Intern and Postgraduate (PG) dental students so as to assess their knowledge, attitude and practice (KAP)

of antibiotic use and its resistance from an academic as well as practical point of view.

The study's findings indicated that the PG students demonstrated higher knowledge compared to the Interns & UG students. There was a significant difference in knowledge between interns and PG students. A majority of subjects from all three groups displayed a good attitude, with an overall insignificant difference observed in attitude among the groups. There was a significant difference in the overall practice among the three groups, with a majority of subjects from all three groups displaying fair practices.

The percentage of correct responses to some of the important statements/questions has revealed the difference in KAP among the PG, UG & Intern which has been shown in result section.

Studies of **Kenealy et al** indicate that antibiotics do not alleviate the symptoms or shorten the duration of colds, as these illnesses generally improve on their own within a week or two. In fact, the inappropriate use of antibiotics can lead to unwanted side effects and contribute to antibiotic resistance, making future bacterial infections harder to treat. The use of antibiotics will speed up the recovery of cold and cough?? Majority of the participants in our study felt that antibiotics are not required to treat the symptoms of common cold. As antibiotics are designed to fight bacterial infections and have no effect on viral infections such as the common cold and cough, which are primarily caused by viruses.¹³ A similar response was also observed in study of **Tevatia et al.(2016)** However, study by **Hueng, et al(2014)**⁹ had shown that majority of the participants had a belief that antibiotics can speed up recovery of common cold, cough and a number of other related illnesses arising from viral infections. Some respondents who preferred the use of antibiotics for upper respiratory tract infections. Studies have proven that

there is no benefit from antibiotics in the treatment of common cold. This observation confirms the need for educational intervention. The inappropriate or excessive use of antibiotics contributes significantly to the development of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in various microbial populations. Reducing unnecessary antibiotic usage can help mitigate the spread of resistance and preserve the efficacy of existing antibiotics.¹⁴ Indiscriminate use of antibiotics leads to emergence of antibiotic resistance? In this, majority of the students were well versed with theoretical knowledge about the irrational use of antibiotic use and antibiotic self-medication can lead to antibiotic resistance. **Pulcini C et al (2017)**⁶ which showed that the scores on behaviour towards antibiotics usage was lower for fourth and fifth year medical students when compared with their juniors. Hence there is a need for strict antibiotic policy for its rational usage which was also felt by the participants of our study. The effectiveness of newer antibiotics can be influenced by their appropriate use and the specific pathogens involved, rather than their price tag. Efficacy better, if the antibiotics are newer and costlier? For this most of participant felt that this statement is wrong. Studies have shown that traditional antibiotics, which are typically less expensive, can have similar or even better outcomes for treating common conditions like acute sinusitis compared to their newer, more costly counterparts. In many cases, the overall treatment outcomes may not significantly differ between the two, especially when treating susceptible organisms. Therefore, the effectiveness of antibiotics should always be evaluated in the context of the specific infection being treated, rather than assuming that newer or more expensive antibiotics will inherently provide better results.¹⁵

Educating family members about the consequences of antibiotic misuse is also essential for overall community health. Do you think antibiotic resistance affects

you and your family's health? Majority of participant agree with this statement as antibiotic resistance is a serious public health concern that directly impacts individual and family health, making bacterial infections harder to treat. So, do you think adverse effects can be reduced by using more than two antibiotics at a time? No, using more than two antibiotics can increase adverse effects felt by most of participant. As research of **Berit sientopot et al** (2024) indicates that excessive use of combination therapy may be associated with an increased likelihood of these negative outcomes. Effective antibiotic stewardship is essential to minimize adverse effects and enhance patient safety while combating antibiotic resistance.¹⁶

Majority of participant agree with the abuse of antibiotics is a significant contributor to the development of bacterial resistance. Abuse of antibiotics has become the main cause leading to bacterial resistance. Have you ever taken any antibiotic without physician consultation? Majority of participant said yes to this statement but according to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, antibiotic resistance causes more than 23,000 deaths per year in the United States with more than 2 million Americans infected with antibiotic-resistant pathogens.¹⁷ Self-medication can cause complications and undermine the effectiveness of prescribed treatments in the future.¹⁸ Have you ever taken any antibiotic without physician consultation? This statement is important as it shows attitude of participant towards antibiotics resistance and almost maximum respondent has taken it without physician consultation. But according to research taking antibiotics without consulting a physician is discouraged due to significant health risks, including the potential for inappropriate treatment leading to antibiotic resistance. Do you take the full course of antibiotics prescribed by the doctor? Yes, said majorly by participants and according to researcher stopping antibiotics prematurely, even if symptoms improve, poses several risks. Remaining bacteria

can become resistant to the antibiotic, making future treatments less effective and contributing to the broader issue of antibiotic resistance. This resistance can make infections harder to treat, leading to prolonged illnesses or complications that could have been avoided if the course was completed as intended.¹⁹ Do you stop taking antibiotics when you start feeling better? Here participant has various opinion as major group support by saying no but some bunch of participant stopped taking it after feeling better. As per study by **Tayla Holman (2016)** stopping antibiotics prematurely when symptoms improve is not advisable. It is crucial to complete the full course of antibiotics as prescribed by a healthcare professional to ensure all harmful bacteria are effectively eradicated from the body.²⁰

Saving Leftover Antibiotics for future use is not recommended. Do you save the leftover antibiotics for the future use? No, Most of the participant agree that they have save leftover antibiotics for future use. But storing leftover antibiotics for future use is strongly discouraged due to significant health risks, including the promotion of antibiotic resistance. Many patients have reported saving unused antibiotics to use later, but this practice can lead to inappropriate treatment decisions and exacerbate public health issues related to antibiotic resistance.²¹

Sharing leftover antibiotics with friends or roommates is strongly discouraged for several health-related reasons. Do you give the leftover antibiotics to your friend / roommate if they get sick? No, Giving leftover antibiotics to others is not recommended by participant. Borrowing or sharing antibiotics can lead to inappropriate treatment since the medication may not be suitable for the friend's illness, potentially exacerbating their condition rather than providing relief. For instance, antibiotics that were effective for one person's condition may not be the right choice for another, especially since different infections may require different types or classes of antibiotics.²¹

The strength of the study is that it gives us the insight of KAP in the budding health-care professionals, which guides us to know the pattern and will help us to narrow down the gap between academic knowledge and professional practice. In addition, we have the opportunity to enhance the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) of these students by conducting practical pharmacology sessions every six months. This will ensure that they stay updated on medications, particularly antibiotics, not only during their final year but also during their internship and further. Considering that prescribers play a significant part in the betterment of not only their own patients but also society at large, it is imperative that students be made aware of all the facts and arguments with a sense of responsibility. Therefore, undergraduate education should not only impart knowledge about prescribing antibiotics but also the fundamentals of the antibiotic usage protocol in the medical field. The educational sector in the medical field should consider changing behavior in addition to expanding information in order to increase the effectiveness of treatment. The way that students are taught must take into account their growth, caliber, skill, and information.

Nowadays, Antibiotic resistance is a major topic of discussion among the media and press, also various online forums are available discussing this issue and hence public sector are now becoming much more aware and careful about the antibiotic resistance. Also the internet, media, newspapers are major sources of information especially among the youngsters, therefore knowledge regarding such issues could be gathered through such mediums.

CONCLUSION

The current study concentrated on various facets of undergraduate and graduate instruction that are pertinent to the reasonable prescription of antibiotics and the prevention of resistance, such as knowledge. The students' responses indicated that they were well-versed in the theoretical information regarding the irrational use of antibiotics and the possibility that antibiotic self-medication could result in antibiotic resistance. When it comes to practice, an overall the practice of the three groups with a majority of the subjects from all three groups showing fair practices. An overall average of KAP came out to be moderate. The first part for a rationale prescription and to prevent antibiotic resistance is the knowledge which has been adequately imparted. However, for implementation and to bring it in practice, our study brought into picture the need for concerned and focused effort by formal training for changes to occur in practice. A broader picture would have emerged if the study was done in multiple institutes pan India.

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